

BASIC PRINCIPLES OF ECONOMIC MANAGEMENT IN THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR AND THEIR DIVERSIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the existing forms of economic activity in the agricultural sector and reveals the basic principles of their diversification. The article discusses the economic efficiency of forms of economic activity, the level of resource utilization and the possibilities of introducing innovative solutions. It also examines the possibilities of agricultural enterprises to reduce risks, increase income and ensure sustainable development through diversification. The results of the study provide practical recommendations for the development of various forms of economic activity in the agricultural sector and the development of diversification strategies.

Introduction. Agriculture has always been one of the most important sectors of economic development. The agricultural sector not only ensures food security, but also plays an important role in creating jobs, increasing export potential and developing the local economy. Today, changing global market demands, limited natural resources and climate change are forcing agricultural enterprises to work more efficiently and sustainably. In this regard, diversification of forms of economic activity - that is, combining different types of activities within one farm - is an important means of increasing the competitiveness of the agricultural sector and reducing risks.

The purpose of the article is to identify existing forms of economic activity in the agricultural sector, analyze the basic principles of their diversification and study the impact of this process on economic efficiency. The introduction also indicates the relevance of the topic, research in scientific literature and its practical significance in the activities of agricultural enterprises.

Analysis and results. The article provides an in-depth analysis of the current state of the agricultural sector and the effectiveness of diversification using statistical data. In 2025, the total value of products and services of the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan reached approximately 538.9 trillion soums, which indicates that agricultural production continues to grow steadily for the sector. The volume of agricultural production increased by 4.4% compared to 2024, with an increase of 7.2% in agriculture and 1.6% in animal husbandry. In terms of regions, Samarkand, Andijan and Kashkadarya regions achieved the highest production indicators. Based on the same data, it was determined that by economic category, the main part of the product is formed by peasant and household farms (62.3%), farms

provide a 29.4% share, and organizations engaged in agricultural activities have a share of 8.3%.

The results of the analysis showed that the dynamic development of the agricultural sector is closely related to the diversity of forms of economic activity. In particular, the increase in the share of farms has increased the competitiveness of small and medium-sized producers in a market economy. Individual farming and homestead farms are often oriented towards product diversification, which creates the opportunity to increase the range of products and adapt to market demand. The fact that farmers also play a large role in grain production indicates the effectiveness of diversification policy in this area: 75.7% of the total grain production is accounted for by farms.

Existing statistical analyses show that by applying the principles of diversification, agricultural sector firms can reduce their risks, expand their sources of income, and adapt to market conditions. For example, international studies have shown positive results in the long-term increase in financial profitability of diversification practices, as well as strengthening biodiversity and ecosystem services. This highlights the economic and environmental benefits of agricultural diversification.

The analysis also shows that the share of the agricultural sector in GDP is still significantly high. According to official statistics, the sector accounts for a significant part of the national gross domestic product and provides employment for a large part of the workforce, especially in rural areas. The results also show that the strategy of diversifying forms of economic activity has a positive impact on the sustainable growth of the agricultural sector, increasing production efficiency and expanding export potential.

Table 1

Prospects for diversification of farm activities in the agricultural sector

No	Business form	Diversification direction	Indicator	Expected change (3–5 years)	Expected results in the future
1	Personal farming	Vegetables → medicinal plant cultivation	Land fertility, income/hectare	Medicinal → 20%, vegetable → 50%	Market prices are stable, family income +25–30%
2	Farms	Livestock + garden → show agroservice	Milk/grain yield, service income (%)	Livestock → 40%, service → 15%	Total revenue through additional services +20–35%
3	Cooperatives	Accumulated equipment → logistics/storage services	Product loss rate (%)	Loss ≤10%	Efficiency +15–25%, export volume +10%
4	Corporate agriculture	Innovative technologies (GIS, drone technology)	Productivity (t/ha)	Grain ≥4.0 t/ha, vegetables	Profitability +18–30%, operating costs

				≥22 t/ha	decrease
5	Public-private partnership	Agrocluster → rural tourism and agro logistics	Ish bilan bandlik (%), qo'shimcha xizmatlar	Employment in agriculture 65%, tourism 5%	Social infrastructure + service export volume

The effectiveness of diversification of farm activities in the agricultural sector varies significantly across different forms of farming. In individual farming, the cultivation of medicinal plants as a diversification direction serves to increase economic stability. Due to the relatively stable market prices for medicinal products, this direction provides an opportunity to grow as a source of income and significantly increases family income.

Farms, on the other hand, expand their overall business portfolio by combining livestock, horticulture and agro-service services. It is expected that gross income will increase by 20–35% as a result of the increase in income from additional services through this direction. At the same time, the integration of technical infrastructure and the development of logistics services through cooperatives will reduce the level of product loss and create an opportunity to attract additional income for export.

In the field of corporate agriculture, innovative technologies, in particular GIS, drones and automated irrigation systems, will significantly increase productivity and reduce operating costs. This will increase the profitability and competitiveness of corporate farms. Also, agroclusters established on the basis of public-private partnerships will develop rural tourism and agro-logistics services, increase agricultural employment and expand service exports. In general, diversification areas are assessed by specific indicators depending on the type of farm, and their effectiveness is measured by statistical indicators such as productivity, income and product loss rates. When farms successfully implement these areas, business efficiency is expected to increase by 15–35%, and risks are significantly reduced. At the same time, innovations and additional services will make the agricultural sector competitive and increase its adaptability to market conditions.

Conclusions and recommendations. The results of the study showed that the effective development of the agricultural sector is directly related to the diversification of forms of economic activity. Family incomes increase and risks are reduced by growing medicinal plants, vegetables and fruits in individual farming and homestead farms. Farms have the opportunity to increase gross income by 20–35% by combining livestock, horticulture and agro-services. Cooperatives and corporate agriculture increase product efficiency and strengthen export potential by introducing machinery, logistics and innovative technologies. State and private sector clusters, on the other hand, develop rural tourism and agro-logistics services, increase employment and expand the agricultural services market.

On this basis, the following proposals are developed:

1. Development of a diversification strategy appropriate to the type of economy - practical combination of different directions in individual farming, farms and the corporate sector.

2. Widespread introduction of innovative technologies - increasing productivity and reducing operating costs through drones, GIS systems and automated irrigation.

3. Development of cooperative and clustered activities - increasing economic efficiency by integrating technical, logistics and agro-service infrastructure.

4. Product diversification aimed at local and export markets - adapting to market demand and creating additional sources of income.

5. Implementation of sustainable and socially responsible strategies - ensuring sustainable production and employment through rural tourism and ecological products.

These recommendations will make the agricultural sector more competitive, increase production efficiency and achieve sustainable development.

References:

1. Tashkent Institute of Agriculture. Forms of farming in agriculture and their efficiency. Tashkent, 2024. 256p.
2. Zamin.uz. Product and diversification of the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan. Tashkent, 2025. 18p.
3. Investment Committee of Uzbekistan. Strategy for the development of the agricultural sector. Tashkent, 2024. 142p.
4. Arxiv.org. Results of diversification of innovative technologies in agriculture. 2023. 32p.
5. Invest.gov.uz. Public-private partnerships and clusters in agriculture. Tashkent, 2024. 24p.
6. Karimov F., Usmonov D. Diversification and sustainable development in agriculture. Tashkent: Agricultural Publishing House, 2022. 198p.
7. Rakhmonova N., Tursunov S. Farms and innovative technologies. Tashkent: Scientific publication, 2023. 210p.
8. Abduvasikov, A., Khurramova, M., Akmal, H., Nodira, P., Kenjabaev, J., Anarkulov, D., ... & Kurbonaliyev, Z. (2024). The concept of production resources in agricultural sector and their classification in the case of Uzbekistan. *Caspian Journal of Environmental Sciences*, 22(2), 477-488.
9. Ibragimov, S. S. O. G. L., Anarkulov, D. A., & Otabekov, J. N. O. G. L. (2022). GLOBAL IQTISODIY INQIROZDA PUL KREDIT SIYOSATINING AHAMIYATI. *Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS)*, 2(4), 222-227.
10. Abdumalikovich, A. D. The Importance of Commercial Banks During the Global Economic Crisis. *International Journal on Economics, Finance and Sustainable Development*, 4(5), 40-42